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“TIMING CLOSURE IN SOC BY ENGINEERING CHANGE ORDER”

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In

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ABSTRACT

With ever increasing IC complexity and aggressive technology scaling towards cutting edge technologies, the SOC timing closure is becoming a tedious, time consuming and challenging task. Also in advanced technology nodes one has to consider the effect of PVT variation, temperature inversion, noise effect on delay, which is adding more scenarios for STA to cover. In this work, we have proposed an algorithm for simultaneous usage of data path ECO and clock path ECO for efficient timing closure in SOC. The algorithm here tries to fix multiple failing end points through simple clock path optimization, instead of performing data path optimization across multiple paths, thus reducing area and power overhead. The proposed algorithm is tested on multiple industrial design and found to achieve 31.7% improvement interms of Worst Negative Slack, 61.9% interms of Total Negative Slack, 60.3% interms of Failing End Points. Also the algorithm is physically aware meaning that the placement blockages, congestions are considered while inserting buffers. The algorithm works under Distributed Multi Scenarios Analysis (DMSA) environment and considers the effect of ECO across multiple corners and modes.

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Dear Author,

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ECO	Engineering Change Order
SOC	System on Chip
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuits
CMOS	Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor
IC	Integrated Circuits
STA	Static Timing Analysis
RTL	Register Transfer Logic
CTS	Clock Tree Synthesis
FC	Full Chip
DRC	Design Rule Constraints
P&R	Place & Route
DMSA	Distributed Multi Scenario Analysis
MCMC	Multi Corner Multi Mode
SPEF	Standard Parasitic Extraction Format
SDC	Synopsys Design Constraints
SDF	Standard Delay Format
WNS	Worst Negative Slack
TNS	Total Negative Slack
FEP	Failing End Points
QoR	Quality of Report
ERC	Electrical Rule Check
AON	Always ON
V _{th}	Threshold Voltage
PVT	Process Voltage Temperature
LEF	Library Exchange Format
DEF	Design Exchange Format
DB	Database
AOCV	Advanced On Chip Variation
POCV	Parametric On Chip Variation
CRPR	Clock Reconvergence Pessimism Removal

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 ENGINEERING CHANGE ORDER

Timing closure implies meeting the timing constraints and it is one of the key issue in physical design. Timing constraints mainly comprises of setup and hold time constraints. Signoff timing analysis is still considered as a critical element in the SoC design flow. With the advancements of the leading edge technologies towards the deep submicron, the performance of a multi-million transistor SoC is challenged by the process variations and design complexity. It has been noticed that integrated circuits in deep submicron technologies with 14nm or less, shows increased timing problems, verification cost and timing closure challenges due to increase in clock frequencies, increased design complexity and increased wire delays. These issues result in increased effort for clock distribution and mainly increases design cycle time. Many methods to overcome the timing closure problems are already proposed such as gate sizing, buffer insertion, netlist restructuring, retiming, boundary optimization etc. One of the upcoming technologies for timing closure is Timing Engineering Change Order (ECO) which efficiently uses buffers to speed-up the circuit or as delay elements.

A semiconductor chip undergoes synthesis, placement, clock tree synthesis and routing processes before going for fabrication. Since all these processes are time consuming, it takes lot of time for a new chip to be sent for fabrication. As a result of cut-throat competition, all the semiconductor companies stress on cycle-time reduction, to be ahead of others in the race. Engineering change orders (ECO) is one of the important technology used for accomplishing the design changes in integrated circuit (IC) and compensate the design bugs at later stages of design cycle. Traditionally, if there is a bug in the design, new photomasks were required for all layers. But photomasks in deep submicron fabrication process are very costly. So in order to save money, ECO technologies are used to modify only a few of the metal layers.

In world of large number of multi-scenarios, the engineering change order (ECO) becomes inevitable to achieve design timing closure with low cost. This concern is attributed to the fact that, performing ECOs is an experimental process requiring an expert. Absence of such an ECO implementation system requires an involvement of huge

manual effort, utilizing scripts leads to significant amount of iterations to achieve its final goal. This causes non convergence of timing closure, making the design prone to the ping-pong effect. This becomes a bottleneck to the design cycle time. Additionally, this approach requires large memory usage and licensed CPU resources which are already very limited. So there is a need of fixing of timing violations across multi-scenarios, gaining significant cycle time in overall timing closure thereby reducing the manual effort.

Fig 1.1 General ECO Flow

There are different types of ECO:

1. **Timing ECO:** To improve timing, to fix setup and hold violations, to fix DRC violations.
2. **Functional ECO:** To change functionality at later stages of design cycle.

Based on whether the database is freeze or not, we can have one more classification of ECO.

1. **Unconstrained ECO:** This is also called as all layer ECO or non-freeze silicon ECO, because there will be no restrictions to the changes in design layout. Before mask generation, it is possible to do all layer ECO at any stage of design cycle including placement, CTS or route.
2. **Freeze silicon ECO:** After the chip is sent for tape out, if there are any changes in the design that need to be accomplished, metal mask ECO are done to save significant cost of mask generation. The design changes are done by using the available spare cells/extra cells in the design and there is no chance of adding extra cells to the design. Here no changes are permitted on the base layers and all base layers will be freeze.

Compared to freeze silicon based ECO, pre silicon based ECO are also very important and plays a significant role in SOC timing closure. Once the design is placed and routed, if there is a bug in the design which is causing the functional failure or timing violation, resynthesizing the design and carrying out placement and routing again is not a feasible as it is time consuming. So there is an immense need of efficient ECO technique to handle these last minute changes.

Most of the timing ECO techniques which are already proposed concentrates on the data path optimization for fixing setup/ hold. These data path optimization are done either by cell sizing (increasing the drive strength) or inserting buffers. In some cases, routing with higher metal layer, changing cell to low Vt cell also accomplishes the purpose. As majority of the ECO techniques tries to optimize data path, they doesn't touch clock path. But one can think of touching the clock path and experiment on Clock Tree Synthesis (CTS). Clock path rescheduling means performing clock push/ pull (Clock tuning) by inserting or removing clock buffers. Primetime ECO covers almost all options for buffer insertion and gate sizing. But it doesn't support clock tree ECO means the tool cannot optimize the cells present in launch/capture clock path. So performing Clock Tree ECO is one of the interesting and challenging tasks which is covered in this work. The idea is to utilize the positive slacks at the fanout cone of the clock tree element as a safe margin and then fix the negative slacks on other paths incrementally through clock tree restructuring/ resizing. [18]

1.2 MOTIVATION

With ASIC design size increasing exponentially every year, the SOC timing signoff & timing ECO phase has increased their weight in terms of overall project time. Currently industries are working with designs having billions of transistors, and using cutting edge technology nodes with 14nm and less. In such case the temperature inversion, power related analysis and noise bring multiple corners and multiple modes for STA to cover. With such big design, a single timing ECO run may take 3 to 5 days. The turn-around-time for timing ECO and timing signoff has become a bottle neck in the later stage of the project. So there is an immense need of effective implementation of ECO with new technologies including physically aware ECO and Clock Tree ECO implementation with less resource, reduced design cycle time and reduced manual effort.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

To propose an efficient ECO technique with fast turn-around-time, which will reduce the size of ECO patch by performing both data path and clock path ECO. The method should be physically aware and also work under multiple corners and multiple modes by consuming less resource and manual effort.

1.4 PROBLEM DEFINITION

What is ECO? Where it falls in the SoC design flow?

ECO involves modifying the synthesized or P&R netlist to meet timing, DRC, Power or Functionality requirements. Modification in the netlist is done by sizing cells, inserting or removing buffer, swapping cells, renaming cells or nets, manual netlist editing etc. Sometimes, the new netlist to be produced may be an incremental change over an existing one. In such a case, there may not be the need to go over the complete cycle. However, everything may be carried out in incremental manner so as to reduce engineering costs, memory requirement, manufacture costs and turnaround time.

Fig 1.2 Detailed ECO Flow

As shown in Figure, the ECO process starts with change in the gate level netlist. The designer needs to change the definitions in RTL by editing the gate-level netlist. The resulting netlist (synthesized from the modified netlist) is then compared with the golden netlist being implemented. The logic causing the difference is then implemented into the

main netlist as a patch. This netlist undergoes placement of the incremental logic, clock tree modifications and routing optimizations based upon the requirements.

Fig 1.3 Primetime timing ECO flow

ECO patch generation and Back annotation: If there exists any timing violations during the timing analysis, the ECO change list is generated by gate sizing/buffer insertion. These changes are implemented in the design using implementation tools like ICC compiler of Synopsys. In timing analysis, to calculate the delays of the nets, parasitic extraction (R & C) is needed. Moreover it is required for noise and crosstalk analysis, IR drop analysis. Before floorplanning or layout, wireload models are used to estimate the parasitic resistance, capacitance and the area due to interconnect. Post layout, routed nets are extracted to get the R & C values and are back-annotated on to the design to get accurate timing. Thus performing ECO is an iterative process requiring few cycles of extraction and back annotation.

1.5 OBJECTIVE

- **Timing ECO:** Formulating algorithm for Timing_ECO. This includes Buffer insertion, cell sizing, vt swap to fix setup and hold violation. Followed by writing tickle script to generate change list for a design. Compare the algorithm results with the results of primetime_ECO flow.

- **Basics of timing Quality Checks:** To carry out a comprehensive study on different types of timing quality/signoff checks, which aids to timing closure in SOC.
- **Physically aware ECO:** Involves Area recovery, Setup fixing, Max Cap fixing, Slow Slope fixing, Hold time fixing. In physically aware ECO, one can account for placement and routing congestion while doing ECO.
- **ECO in DMSA (Distributed Multi Scenario Analysis) environment:** Checking the effect of ECO patch in MCMM (Multiple Corner Multiple Mode) environment. This mainly reduces the resource usage, number of iterations, design closure time and manual effort.
- **ECO by incremental SPEF extraction using StarRC:** To carry out ECO in incremental manner using StarRC extraction. Here we generate the change list file and implement the changes with the IC Compiler place and route tool. Then we can perform incremental parasitic extraction on the updated design with the StarRC extraction tool. To complete signoff, rerun primetime static timing analysis with the incremental extraction data. Compare the improvement in run time by using incremental SPEF compared to normal ECO flow.
- **Full Chip Min delay convergence:** Min/Hold fix flow considering full chip (FC) context to partition level. The idea behind this is to let partition level run have all relevant full chip point of view. This will shorten overall interface min delay closure time for SoC. Here we generate a context from full chip which contains the port list where there is a setup slack available and the hold fix can be done. Load this context file during the partition timing runs and then perform ECO.
- **Simultaneous Data path and Clock path ECO:** To develop an algorithm for clock ECO. The main idea of the algorithm would be to search a node in the design where the clock ECOs can be placed without affecting the setup and hold of non-violating path and to write the tcl script to generate clock ECO.

1.6 OUTLINE OF THE REPORT

This report is organized as chapters covering different aspect of timing Engineering Change Order.

Chapter 2 – *Literature survey*: This chapter gives an overview of related works in the field of Engineering Change Order.

Chapter 3 - *Static Timing Analysis (STA) concepts and guidelines for timing closure*: This chapter describes the timing verification flow, important STA terminologies, followed by the guidelines for efficient timing closure.

Chapter 4 - *Methodology: Basic timing ECO flow*: This chapter gives a brief overview on different methods available for timing ECO, basic ECO flow, utilities of primetime to support ECO flow.

Chapter 5 - *Improvements to timing ECO flow*: In this chapter the improvements to basic ECO flow, including physically aware ECO, ECO by incremental SPEF extraction, ECO in DMSA environment and context flow for min delay convergence are discussed.

Chapter 6 - *Simultaneous data path and clock path Engineering Change Order*: This chapter discusses on the Proposed Methodology for simultaneous data path and clock path ECO and the concepts of useful skew.

Chapter 7 – *Results, Conclusion & Future Scope*: Conclusion on the project work and future work that can be done for enhancement of the clock ECO are discussed.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

This chapter covers some of the literatures that address the timing closure problem and provides related solution. In [1] Chen et al. used gate sizing and buffer insertion techniques to fix paths which violate the timing constraint and Ho et al. [2] iteratively performed timing optimization until no timing violation paths remains. In [3], a Unified approach for simultaneous functional and timing ECO is proposed. [4] Discusses on Topology-Aware Buffer Insertion for ECO Timing Optimization. In [5], Z. Li and W. Shi proposed a new algorithm for optimal buffer insertion.

The problem of minimizing the inserted delays for removing hold violations has been studied extensively in [7, 8, 9, 10, 11], and these delay insertion technique can also be used in clock period minimization. Huang et al. [8] proposed a solution to solve hold violation by minimizing the number of buffer insertions. Tu et al. [11] tried fix hold violations under different power modes for ultra-low voltage designs assuming that any inserted delay can be realized by unit delay elements. In [12], optimization flow to solve hold violations by inserting buffers as delay elements is proposed. This paper discusses on linear programming based approach that captures the different delays introduced between setup constraints and hold time constraints due to different cell libraries specified for the constraints.

Apart from timing ECO, there are also researches going on to improve the efficiency ECO during backend flow. Some papers also discusses on metal- only ECO flow. [13] Tan and Jiang describe a typical metal only ECO flow with four steps that include placement and spare cell distribution, logic difference extraction, metal-only ECO synthesis, and ECO routing. Lin et al. addressed logic synthesis techniques for engineering change problems [14]. Shinsha et al. performed incremental logic synthesis through gate logic structure identification [15]. Swamy et al. achieved minimal logic resynthesis for engineering change [16]. Watanabe and Brayton presented another kind of incremental synthesis technique for engineering changes [17].

Timing aware Functional ECO using space cells in the design is discussed in [19]. This paper focus on incorporating functional ECOs in the design with the available spare cells in the design. While doing this, author considered timing delay impact and wiring cost. Also many spare cells in the design may not be used and unnecessarily increase chip area. So accomplishing functional ECO through constant insertion avoids unnecessary usage of extra spare cells. The technology mapping to spare cell is done by one of the following techniques. NOR, NAND, DeMorgan's Theorems, Constant insertion as shown.

Fig 2.1 Example for ECO using spare cell [19]

Fig 2.2 Technology mapping to spare cells [19]

[20] Discuss on utilizing clock skew for timing reliability improvement. This paper focus on increasing the timing reliability of a circuit by exploiting the permissible clock skew range of each local data path.

Clock Rescheduling for Timing Engineering Change Orders is proposed in [21]. This paper addresses the problem in the sequential domain to explore more optimization flexibility. Here author proposed an orthogonal method of post-mask clock scheduling

with spare cells. In this paper, along with gate sizing and buffer insertion techniques, wire snaking technique is also used as a solution to fix timing violations.

Fig 2.3 Example ECO clock rescheduling [21]

[22] Talks about challenges in clock path ECO technique. 3 solutions are proposed for the same including upsizing D flipflops, choosing best re-stitching point on clock tree structure and use the concept of time borrowing to fix the timing violations and talks about in-law clock tree method.

Fig 2.4 Clock re-stitching using time borrowing [22]

CHAPTER 3

STATIC TIMING ANALYSIS (STA) CONCEPTS AND GUIDELINES FOR TIMING CLOSURE

Before moving towards timing ECO, it is important to understand some of the concepts related to timing analysis. The aim of Static Timing Analysis (STA) is to check whether the design meets clock frequency/speed under multiple corners and modes. Static timing analysis is the most accurate approach to analyze the timing performance of a design before performing dynamic timing analysis through extensive test benches. This is where Synopsys PrimeTime comes into the ASIC design flow. It has the ability to analyze a design over various temperatures, voltages and process variations and this makes a designer feel that a very robust design has been produced.

Fig 3.1 STA in backend flow [23]

Starting from an RTL design, the Design Compiler tool generates a gate-level design. The PrimeTime tool reads the gate-level description (Verilog, VHDL) and reads various standard cell and macro library (.db) to get timing information. Next input is the

Synopsys Design Constraints (SDC) file which is used for specifying clock characteristics, timing exceptions and case and mode analysis settings etc. If PrimeTime finds any timing violations, Design Compiler can resynthesize the design using new timing constraints to fix the conditions that cause the timing violations. When the gate-level design is free of timing violations, the design can proceed to placement and routing. This produces a chip layout database. Accurate delay information/ parasitic information (Standard Parasitic Extraction Format) are extracted and back-annotated on the design to get physically accurate timing analysis. If the design has timing violations, PrimeTime can generate an Engineering Change Order (ECO) change list to fix the violations. After the timing violations are resolved, PrimeTime can also generate an ECO change list that optimizes timing, area and power. IC Compiler uses the ECO change list to implement the changes. After successful validating the design timing, the completed design is signed off.

Fig 3.2 Implementation Flow using PrimeTime [24]

A liberty file contains operating conditions (Process, Voltage, Temperature), derating factors to account for the PVT variations, limits such as maximum input slew, maximum output capacitance etc., units, lookup table templates, description of several attributes of a standard cell such as timing information, area specification, function specification, SDF condition, pin capacitance of a standard cell etc. For delay modelling,

table look up (Non Linear Delay Model) is used. Timing information includes delay modelling for various combinational and sequential cells w.r.t. rise delay, fall delay, rise transition, fall transition based on output capacitance and input transition along with different SDF conditions. Timing sense of each of the arcs of the cell is also given. Slew and delay also depends on the threshold points. Power information contains internal power (rise and fall) based on output capacitance and input transition and related to an input pin, leakage power information depending on various input states etc. Pulse width definitions of clocks, recovery & removal time requirements for asynchronous set and reset pins are specified. Pin capacitance information includes max capacitance, min capacitance, timing sense, maxcap lookup table based on frequency. For sequential elements, data pin is characterized w.r.t. clock pin by setup and hold constraints and asynchronous pins (reset & preset) are characterized by recovery & removal checks.

```
# Include all libraries - technology and IP model libraries
set link_path "* my_tech_lib.db memory_lib.db"

# Read all gate-level design files
read_verilog my_full_chip.v

# Read libraries and link the design
link_design MY_FULL_CHIP

# Set up bc_wc analysis with 2 SDF. Wait for checks later
read_sdf -analysis_type bc_wc -max_type sdf_max -min_type sdf_min

# Apply chip-level constraints for pre or post layout analysis
source MY_FULL_CHIP_CONST.tcl
```

Fig 3.3 Inputs and steps to create PrimeTime session

3.1 TIMING CONCEPTS

3.1.1 Timing/ Constraints checks: STA performs check for violations of timing constraints, such as setup and hold constraints, recovery and removal constraints, clock-gating setup and hold constraints, data-to-data constraints and minimum pulse width.

Setup Check: Verification that data becomes valid and stable for a minimum time before being captured by flip-flop.

Hold Check: Verify that data remains stable for a minimum time as required by capture flip-flop.

Fig 3.4 Setup and Hold check

The amount of time by which a violation is avoided is called the *slack*. A negative slack indicates a timing violation.

EQN 1 $Slack_{setup} = \text{Data Required Time} - \text{Data Arrival Time} \geq 0$

EQN 2 $T_{capture} - t_{FF2setup} \geq T_{launch} + t_{FF1clk2Q} + t_M$

Clk Spec Library Clk Spec Library Cell + Net

EQN 1 $Slack_{hold} = \text{Data Arrival Time} - \text{Data Required Time} \geq 0$

EQN 2 $T_{launch} + t_{FF1clk2Q} + t_M \geq T_{capture} + t_{FF2hold}$

Clk Spec Library Cell + Net Clk Spec Library

Fig 3.5 Setup and Hold slack equation

Recovery and removal check is performed on asynchronous signals like reset/set while de-asserting with respect to clock. Generally assertion is done asynchronously. Recovery time is the minimum required time before the next active clock edge before which the reset must be released. Similarly, Removal time is the minimum

required time after the clock edge after which reset can be released. These checks are done to prevent functional/metastability issues by ensuring that the reset removal does not occur for different flops at different clock edges.

Fig 3.6 Recovery and Removal check

3.1.2 Delay variation with PVT:

Voltage Variation: When voltage is high, current through the device increases and devices

are fast resulting in less cell delay and vice versa. So, the high voltage corner (say 1.1 V) is critical for hold analysis and low voltage corner (say 0.9 V) is critical for setup analysis. The voltage variation effects are modelled in the liberty (.lib) file and read by PrimeTime while doing timing verification.

Process Variation: Process or technology nodes (e.g. 90 nm, 65 nm, 22 nm) are characteristic of any technology and represents the channel length of the smallest transistor used in the design. As transistor length increases, current through the device decreases and the device delay increases. Process variation refers to variation in transistor length, width, doping density, oxide thickness which might cause threshold voltage/current variation. Three types of libraries are available to account for the process variation- typical, fast and slow. The easy way to incorporate the process variation is to read in the typical lib and use timing derates to model the fast and slow phenomena.

Temperature Variation: The surrounding temperature also impacts timing behavior of a chip. Higher the temperature, more the collision rate of electrons within the device, less is the mobility and current through device, more is the delay.

Fig 3.7 Variation of delay with PVT corner

3.1.3 Timing path:

When performing timing analysis, PrimeTime first breaks down the design into timing paths.

Fig 3.8 Timing paths

Each timing path consists of the following elements

- Startpoint: The start of a timing path where data is launched by a clock edge or where the data must be available at a specific time. Every startpoint must be either an input port or a register clock pin.

- Combinational logic network: Elements that have no memory or internal state. Combinational logic can contain AND, OR, XOR, and inverter elements, but cannot contain flip-flops, latches, registers, or RAM.
- Endpoint: The end of a timing path where data is captured by a clock edge or where the data must be available at a specific time. Every endpoint must be either a register data input pin or an output port.

PrimeTime also considers the following types of paths for timing analysis:

Path	From	To
Clock path	clock input port or cell pin	clock pin of a sequential element
Clock-gating path	input port	clock-gating element
Asynchronous path	input port	set or clear pin of a sequential element

Fig 3.9 Types of paths considered for timing analysis

Path groups: For the purpose of ease of analyzing the design, all the timing paths are sorted into separate groups, called Path Groups based on the same endpoint clock. Example, REG-TO-REG, IN-TO-REG, REG-TO-OUT, IN-TO-OUT or Feedthrough.

The total delay of a path is the sum of all cell and net delays in the path.

3.1.4 Clock skew and clock latency:

Skew is the difference in timing between two or more signals, maybe data, clock or both. The end points of a clock tree are typically clock pins of synchronous elements, such as flip-flops. Clock latency is the total time it takes from the clock source to an end point. Clock skew is the difference in arrival times at the end points of the clock tree.

Fig 3.10 Clock skew and clock latency

3.2 APPROACHES / GUIDELINES FAST TIMING CLOSURE

- Follow a methodical approach and recommended coding guidelines
- Constrain the design correctly and completely
- Provide timing models for black boxes and remove unresolved references
- Correct synthesis timing errors before going to place and route
- Understand and apply information from the timing report in subsequent runs
- Address issues early in the flow. Handle failing paths by focusing on the reason for the failure
- For paths with more net delay or inefficient placement, increase the placement effort in the place and route tool.
- If high fanout causes timing failure, try replicating the net or net driver during synthesis or apply a tighter timing constraint on that path.
- Use ECO techniques in an efficient way for faster timing closure

3.2.1 Recommended guidelines for constraining the design:

Correctly constraining the design helps with faster timing closure. Create SDC file for the design by following these guidelines:

- Properly define all primary clocks and generated clocks in the design
- Do not define gated clocks. Defining gated clocks prevents clock conversion, which may affect timing QoR.

- Plan clock and data pin location assignments early in the project, as they can have significant effects throughout the design. Effects can include excessive clock skew, poor I/O timing, timing hazardous clock domain crossing, less flexible logic placement, fewer clocking resource choices, excessive routing delays, and reduced device utilization.
- Provide realistic clock constraints. Under constraining or over constraining the design can result in reduced performance.
- Put unrelated clocks in separate clock groups. When clocks are in the same group, the software will do cross clock domain timing analysis. If clocks are defined in different or asynchronous groups, the tool does not perform timing analysis.
- Define input delay and output delay constraints for all inputs and outputs in the design. If the inputs and outputs are left unconstrained, the tool treats the paths as false paths and does no timing optimization on them.
- Properly define timing exceptions (false paths and multicycle paths). Doing so enables the tool to ignore those paths. Incorrectly defining timing exceptions forces the tool to do unnecessary optimizations.
- Provide timing models for black boxes.
- If a timing path is constrained with multiple constraints, the constraint with higher priority overrides the other. For example, if a false path and a max delay constraint are defined on the same path, then the false path constraint is applied and the max delay constraint is ignored.

3.2.2 Some of the recommended coding guidelines:

- **Latches:** Latches run at a lower frequency, so do not use them unless required by the design. Consider using edge-triggered flip-flops instead. Make sure not to omit the final else / default of if or case statement in the RTL code. This can generate a latch. The don't care (X) assignments on default conditions prevent latch generation. For best logic optimization, assign the default case or final else value to don't care (X) instead of a logic value. Check for any latches that are inferred in the netlist and change RTL code to fix all unintentional latch inferences.
- **Combinational Loops:** Avoid combinational loops in the design. Combinational loops reduce the operating frequency of a design.

- **Tristate Signals:** Tristate signals should be attached to top-level bidirectional or output ports. Avoid bidirectional ports in lower level modules or assigning a Z logic value, unless it is driving an output or bidirectional port.
- **HDL Code:** Write HDL code such that there is a match the device architecture and HDL code as closely as possible. To define HDL code for control signals, make sure to follow architecture specific control signal priority to avoid extra logic being implemented for the design.
- **Fanout Nets:** Drive high fanout nets from a synchronous start point such as a flip-flop. Avoid driving more loads from a combinational gate.
- **Clocks:** The number of clocks used in the design should be minimum and use only one edge of the clock. Utilize dedicated hardware to perform clock multiplexing, instead of coding it in RTL as it can introduce delay in the combinational logic.
- **Crossing Clock Domains:** Ensure that signals crossing clock domains are properly synchronized. Use a synchronizer, which is a handshake mechanism or a FIFO to implement the same.

CHAPTER 4

METHODOLOGY: BASIC TIMING ECO FLOW

This chapter discusses the algorithm for Timing ECO along with the flow chart. In the design if there are any timing or noise violations or design rule issues, Engineering Change Order (ECO) flow is used to fix the violations. The changes are implemented by sourcing the change list and timing analysis is carried out again to check whether all the violations are fixed or not. Setup fixing honors DRC and alters hold slack if needed; hold fixing honors setup slack and DRC. Therefore we fix DRC violations followed by setup violations followed by hold violations in ECO flow.

Fixing stages	Description
Fix clock ERC	fixing max cap/ slope on clock network
Fix ERC	fixing ERC violations
Fix setup	fixing setup violations
Fix power	fixing leakage power
Fix hold	fixing hold violations
Fix endpoints	fixing hold violations leftovers
Fix aggressive	fixing hold violations left due to some SNPS issue
Fix AON (always ON)	for handling nominal cells in AON power domains

Table 4.1 Different fixing stages during ECO

4.1 FIX TECHNIQUES FOR ENGINEERING CHANGE ORDER

There are different techniques for Timing ECO

- Multi Vth swapping
- Sizing cells
- Inserting or removing buffer
- Swapping cells
- Renaming cells or nets

➤ Manual netlist editing

1. Vth Swapping:

Speed of a circuit is usually governed by how fast the output capacitor charges or discharges. The threshold voltage dictates the transistor switching speed, that is it determines what is the minimum voltage required to charge the capacitor. Higher the threshold voltage, higher the oxide thickness, more time the capacitor takes to charge, to reach to that level, decreasing its speed. Thus to reduce the delta delay on the net, the gate delay or the cell delay of the driver cell needs to be reduced, which is done by swapping the cell with its equivalent Low Threshold Voltage Cell (LVT) cell available in the libraries. Switching to LVT cell, having low oxide thickness, ensures that the time taken by the cell to switch its output is less, increasing its speed. However, decreasing the threshold voltage also results in leakage related problems. At low threshold voltages, the power increases with the increase in transient current.

2. Driver Upsizing:

Another technique of reducing the delay is upsizing the driver cell for improving the output drive strength of cell. Upsizing the cell means, increasing the width of the transistor which effectively decreases the resistance of the cell, resulting in increased current. From the Elmore Delay calculation of a cell shows that a cell can be replaced by its equivalent RC network and its delay (τ) is given by,

$$\tau = 0.69 R_{int} * C_{eff}$$

Where τ is the delay of the cell, R_{int} total internal resistance of the cell, C_{eff} is effective internal and load capacitance.

$$I_{mossat} = [\mu * C_{ox} * W * (V_{gs} - V_t)^2 * (1 + \lambda * V_{ds})] / L$$

$$R_{int} \propto 1 / \text{Width of the transistor}$$

Thus, by scaling the transistor when the output load is fixed, that is increasing its width decreases the resistance and increases the drive. So, Upsizing the cell improves the output transition, reduces the propagation delay time of the cell improving the drive strength. However, from $C_{gate} = C_{ox}WL$ where C_{gate} is the gate capacitance. Increasing the width of the cell also increases the gate and parasitic capacitances, which provides larger load in the fanin of the cell.

3. Buffer Insertion:

This is an effective technique for interconnect driven timing optimization. The interconnect delay is directly proportional to the square of the interconnect length. Inserting buffers in smaller segments, makes interconnect delay linearly proportional to the wire length. It reduces the elmore delay of the nets by driving net capacitances through smaller resistances, thereby improving the slack of the path. However, it increases the area drastically along with requiring modifications in the re-routing stage.

Also buffer insertion is used for fixing the DRC violations like transition violation, max capacitance violation and max fanout violation by sharing the load.

Fig 4.1 Example for load buffering

Fig 4.2 Example for load shielding

NOTE: Both buffer insertion and cell sizing cannot be used together in same command because they are mutually exclusive. Usually cell sizing is done first followed by buffer insertion method in order to gain incremental improvements.

4.2 TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGIES USED

Technology	Tools available
Regular Timing ECO	Synopsys: ECO compiler (before), Primetime-ECO (now). Tweaker-f1 & tweaker-t1 are also used in recent days.
Functional ECO	Cadence design systems: Conformal ECO
ECO in DMSA Environment	Synopsys: Primetime-ECO
Physically aware ECO	Synopsys: Primetime-ECO / Tweaker ECO/ Dorado
ECO by Incremental SPEF extraction	Synopsys: Primetime-ECO + StarRC
Min Fix Flow	Synopsys: Primetime Hyperscale context
Power ECO	Synopsys: PTPX
Noise and DRC ECO	Synopsys: PTSI
Clock ECO	Synopsys: Primetime-ECO + IC compiler

Table 4.2 Tools used for ECO

4.3 SIMPLE TIMING ECO

Based on the drive strengths either Vth swapping is chosen or upsizing (upsized to the maximum size available except for don't touch and don't use cell list). The alternative cell with the best input slew is chosen for replacement. Its slew value is compared against the path slack value. If it's lesser than that, the driver cell is successfully replaced with this alternative cell and the value equivalent to path slack value is updated for the next inner iteration. The slew value is compared with slack value as the ultimate goal is to eliminate the timing violation. After successful replacement, the next worst net from the list is considered. This inner iteration, of finding the worst affected net, its details and its driver cell details followed by replacement, over the list of nets of a particular path continues till either the slack of the path significantly improves or the list gets exhausted. In such a case, the next path of a group is taken into consideration. And after all the paths of a group have been analyzed, the next group is considered. Figure 4.3 shows the flow chart of simple timing ECO flow and the corresponding ECO patch generated by the ECO flow is shown in figure 4.4

Fig 4.3 Flow chart of Timing ECO flow

```

1 ## ECO commands
2 size_cell {u_i2c_slave/U3_ICC_cts} stdlib/BUFX8
3 insert_buffer {ck_rst_gen/U29/Y} {stdlib/BUFX2}
4 create_cell {xlm48901/eco_diode_1} {ANTENNA5}
5 set_attribute [get_cells -all {xlm48901/eco_diode_1}] origin "2519.127 0.000"
6 connect_net {xlm48901/adc_1_enable} {xlm48901/eco_diode_1/A}

```

Fig 4.4 Example ECO patch/ change list

4.4 TIMING QUALITY CHECKS BEFORE ECO

Quality check includes a set of verification steps that must be passed before the design is sent for tape out. Quality check tools contain set of rules written in a particular scripting language. Choice of scripting language is generally decided based on the base language of tool (Eg. tickle, Perl). Main motto of using these quality check tool would be to analyze and debug the quality check violations and clean the design. The tool will includes set of quality checks for clocking, connectivity, timing, DRC etc. There will be some standard which is known as "golden" or signoff-quality. Goal is to improve the design w.r.t. the measuring criteria to meet the sign-off quality. E.g. the clock manipulation elements can modify the pulse width of the clock signal or may change the clock waveform which might be unable to switch the state of the driven sequential. They may change the clock polarity sometimes. So these can be quality hazards and may result in problems in silicon.

4.4.1 Design Rule Constraints:

- **Max transition:** Defined for input pin. This is the max time taken by the net to change its logic value. If the transition of a net is more/ bad, delay also will be huge. This info is present in .lib file
- **Max capacitance:** Defined for output pin. This denotes the max capacitive load the output pin can drive. This comprises of both pin and interconnect net capacitance. This info is present in .lib file
- **Max fan-out:** Defined for output pin. This is the max number of the input pins, which the particular output can drive. ie it denotes the load driving capacity of that pin. This info is present in .lib file

4.4.1.1 Max transition /Slow Slope effect on Timing:

- Transition time depends on rise time and fall time (Slew) & is based on the library data.

Fig 4.5 Max transition violation [23]

- For Nonlinear delay model (NLDM), Cell delay = f (Input transition, Output load)

Fig 4.6 Non Linear Delay Model (NLDM) [23]

- More the time the input between low level threshold v_{tn} and high level threshold v_{tp} , both NMOS and PMOS will be ON, leading to short circuit power dissipation

➤ Fix Advice:

- Upsize driver
- Decreasing net length by moving cells nearer
- Inserting buffers
- Reduce high fanout nets by splitting loads through buffers
- Route using higher metal layer

```

cell (<cellname>) {
cell_leakage_power : 3.748077e-03;
threshold_voltage_group : "si38p" ;
area : "8.775" ;
....
abc_cell () {
...
pin (Z) {
direction : "output";
}
pin (CP) {
direction : "input";
}
pin (D) {
direction : "input";
}
....
}
pin (CP) {
clock : true;
direction : "input";
related_bias_pin : "VDDB VSSB";
rise_capacitance : 0.001733;
rise_capacitance_range(0.001268,0.002017);
capacitance : 0.001706;
fall_capacitance : 0.001680;
fall_capacitance_range(0.001293,0.001938);
max_transition : 0.550;
....
}
pin (D) {
direction : "input";
related_bias_pin : "VDDB VSSB";
rise_capacitance : 0.000752;
rise_capacitance_range(0.000648,0.000960);
capacitance : 0.000741;
fall_capacitance : 0.000730;
fall_capacitance_range(0.000638,0.000875);
max_transition : 0.800;
related_power_pin : "VDD";
related_ground_pin : "VSS";
....
}
pin (Z) {
direction : "output";
related_bias_pin : "VDDB VSSB";
max_capacitance : 0.334971 ;
max_fanout : 20 ;
...
timing () {
cell_degradation (constraint) {
index_1 ("1.0, 1.5, 2.0") ;
values ("1.0, 1.5, 2.0") ;
}
}
}

```

Fig 4.7 Library snapshot

4.4.1.2 Max Cap effect on Timing:

- Violation of cell output's maximum capacitance
- Results in wrong modeling in reliability verification. More the capacitive load, more the time to charge/discharge to/from a particular logic level. So more the delay. CMOS delay model: Transition Time = Drive R X Load C

Net Fanout	Resistance KΩ	Capacitance pF
1		
2	0.01295	0.00812
3	0.02092	0.01312
4	0.02888	0.01811

Wire Load Model (RC)

Fig 4.8 Wire Load Model (WLM) [23]

- Leads to too much current draw from the power rails. More the load, more the dynamic power consumption

$$P_d = \alpha C v^2 f$$

- **Fix Advice:** Increasing the drive strength of the drive cell

4.4.1.3 Max Fan-out effect on Timing:

- Output net of D1 sees 1000 pin capacitance and hence the transition of that net will be bad
- Thus the input transition for all L* cells will be bad. So the cell delays of L* cells will be high
- Since the transition of the output nets of D1 is bad, the net delays is also high
- For cell D1, since the output load is high, cell delay is also high
- **Fix Advice:** Fixed by buffering. Generally if transition, cap and timing is met, this is not a must fix

Fig 4.9 Example for Max fanout violation

4.4.2 Minimum Pulse Width Constraint:

This check is done to ensure that clock signal width is wide enough to perform cells internal operations. Pulse width of a clock shrinks because of the unequal rise and fall delays of the cells on clock path. This difference arises due to variations and this is more dominant at lower technology nodes. When the signal passes through a series of buffers/inverters or other combinational cells on clock path then its pulse width degrades and at a point when the cell delay is more than the clock pulse width, the clock pulse is absorbed. Jitter can also affect pulse width. Both the high pulse width and the low pulse width should be preserved and it should be greater than a minimum value. This value can vary depending on requirement e.g. it can be $0.5 \times$ high pulse width (or low pulse width) or it can be the library limit or it can be set by the designer.

SEQUENTIAL CLOCK PULSE WIDTH

Pin	Required Pulse Width	Actual Pulse Width	Slack	Clock Name	View Name
clk_ctrl_reg/CP (high)	0.3202	2.9731	2.6529	src_clk	func_min

There are 2 ways to define the pulse width constraint in the design. One by defining timing_type: min_pulse_width in the liberty file. Other by using commands set_max_pulse_width & set_min_pulse_width as shown.

1. Defining timing_type: min_pulse_width in the liberty file

```

pin (CP) {
  clock : true;
  direction : input;
  max_transition : 2.5;
  capacitance : 0.00774191;

  timing () {
    related_pin : "CP";
    timing_type : min_pulse_width;
    rise_constraint (mpw_constraint) {
      index_1 ("0.1, 0.6, 1.3, 1.9, 2.5");
      values ("0.131, 0.800, 1.596, 2.392, 3.066");
    }
    fall_constraint (mpw_constraint) {
      index_1 ("0.1, 0.6, 1.3, 1.9, 2.5");
      values ("0.361, 0.800, 1.596, 2.392, 3.066" );
    }
  }
}

```

2. Setting minimum pulse width constraint using commands

```
set_min_pulse_width -high 3.0 [all_clocks]
```

```
set_min_pulse_width -low 2.0 [all_clocks]
```

4.4.3 Data Cells on Clock Path:

Clock cells are more variation robust. On other hand data cells are not designed to toggle every cycle, so they fail reliability verification if used in a clock context. Also data cells are skewed having different rise and fall delay. Hence they may affect the pulse width of clock signal when used in clock path. This will result in inaccurate timing results.

Fig 4.10 Data Cells on Clock Path

4.5 PRIMETIME UTILITIES TO SUPPORT ECO FLOW

The figure shows the various fixing steps supported in primetime, and the corresponding commands and fixing mechanism.

Steps	Commands	Fixing mechanisms	Precedence rules
Step1: Power recovery	<code>fix_eco_power</code>	Cell sizing, buffer removal	Does not introduce new timing or DRC violations
Step 2: Fix DRC and noise violations	<code>fix_eco_drc</code>	Buffer insertion, cell sizing	Alters setup and hold slacks as needed
Step 3: Fix timing violations	<code>fix_eco_timing</code>	Buffer insertion, cell sizing	Setup fixing honors DRC and alters hold slack if needed; hold fixing honors setup slack and DRC
Step 4: Final leakage recovery	<code>fix_eco_power</code>	Threshold voltage swapping	Does not introduce new timing or DRC violations; does not change layout

Fig 4.11 Primetime ECO steps and commands

4.5.1 Fixing DRC:

1. Make sure to have a design which is fully placed and routed, with stable clock tree.
2. Command to fix DRC violations `fix_eco_drc`

```
fix_eco_drc
  -type max_transition | max_capacitance | max_fanout
  -methods {size_cell insert_buffer} \
```

4.5.2 Fixing timing violation:

1. Make sure to have a design which is fully placed and routed, with stable clock tree
2. To preserve parts of the design that were previously optimized, apply the `dont_touch` attribute to those parts. The ECO fixing commands do not make changes on objects that have the `dont_touch` attribute set to true.
3. Command to fix the setup violations: `fix_eco_timing -type setup`

```
fix_eco_timing
-type setup
-physical_mode open_site | occupied_site
-methods insert_buffer | size_cell
-buffer_list list_of_buffers
```

4. Command to fix the hold violations: `fix_eco_timing -type hold`

```
fix_eco_timing
-type hold
-physical_mode open_site | occupied_site
-methods insert_buffer | size_cell
-buffer_list list_of_buffers
```

5. One can list the alternative library cells for ECO by using `report_eco_library_cells`

```
pt_shell> report_eco_library_cells
```

```
*****
Report : eco_library_cells
...
*****
Alternative library cells:
```

```
Attributes:
  u - dont_use or pt_dont_use
  d - dont_touch
```

Group	Library_cell	Area	Attributes
[0]	core_typical/hvt_buf_1	4.50	
	core_typical/hvt_buf_2	5.40	
	core_typical/hvt_buf_3	6.30	
	core_typical/hvt_dly2	8.10	u
[1]	core_typical/hvt_inv_1	3.60	
	core_typical/hvt_inv_2	4.50	
	core_typical/hvt_inv_3	5.40	

4.5.3 Fixing noise violations:

```
fix_eco_drc -type noise \
-methods {size_cell insert_buffer} \
-physical_mode open_site
```

Primetime also provides facility to perform ECO using GUI, instead of using commands.

Fig 4.12 ECO using primetime GUI

4.13 (a)

4.13 (b)

Fig 4.13 a. Size cell GUI b. Insert buffer GUI in primetime

4.6 MANUAL NETLIST EDITING

We can manually edit the netlist and analyze how the changes affect the timing. This can be useful late in a design cycle when only small edits can be made.

Object	Task	Command
Buffer	Insert a buffer	insert_buffer
	Remove a buffer	remove_buffer
Cell	Change the size (or drive strength) of a cell	size_cell
	Create a cell	create_cell
	Rename a cell	rename_cell
	Remove a cell	remove_cell
Net	Add a new net	create_net
	Connect nets to pins	connect_net
	Disconnect nets from pins	disconnect_net
	Rename a net	rename_net
	Remove a net	remove_net

Fig 4.14 Netlist editing commands

In order to replace or resize cells, find alternative library cells by running the `get_alternative_lib_cells -base_names` command:

```
pt_shell> get_alternative_lib_cells -base_names u1 {"AN2", "AN2i"}
```

Let us consider some simple example for manual netlist editing.

```
pt_shell> size_cell o_reg1 class/FD2P3
Sized 'o_reg1' with 'class/FD2P3'

pt_shell> read_db A.db
pt_shell> current_design TOP
pt_shell> swap_cell {u1 u2 u3} A.db:A

pt_shell> rename_cell cellA cellB
Information: Renamed cell 'cellA' to 'cellB' in design
'middle'. (NED-008)

pt_shell> rename_net [get_nets u1/low/w1] u1/low/netA
Uniquifying 'u1/low' (low) as 'low_0'.
Uniquifying 'u1' (inter) as 'inter_0'.
Information: Renamed net 'w1' to 'netA' in 'middle/u1/low'.
(NED-009)

pt_shell> insert_buffer {u3/A u4/A} class/B1I
```


Fig 4.15 Manual netlist editing by inserting buffer

To improve the efficiency of the ECO flow, use the `estimate_eco` to quickly compute and display the ECO alternatives based on current timing values of a particular stage. The estimate considers the incoming transition times, output loading, fanout loading, detailed parasitic if present, and driver characteristics of the candidate cells.

```
pt_shell> estimate_eco -type size_cell -max -rise
```

delay type : max_rise						
lib	cell	area	stage_delay	arrival	slack	trans
mylib90	CKNXD12	19.05	0.0462	0.0462	0.1474	0.012
mylib90	INVD24	21.17	0.0265	0.0265	0.1671	0.030
mylib90	INVD20	18.35	0.0291	0.0291	0.1645	0.022
mylib90	CKNXD8	14.11	0.0610	0.0610	0.1326	0.105
mylib90	INVD3	3.53	0.1295	0.1295	0.0212	0.199
*mylib90	INVD2	2.82	0.1936	0.1936	-0.0013	0.292
mylib90	CKNXD1	2.82	0.4271	0.4271	-0.3214	0.326

Here the design rule checking estimations include all pins of the cell being resized, previous driver pin and slack-critical load pin.

Fig 4.16 estimate_eco -type size_cell

```
pt_shell> estimate_eco -type insert_buffer -inverter_pair \  
-max -rise -verbose \  
-lib_cells INVD
```

```
cell name : buf3  
current lib cell: mylib90/INVD2  
buffer lib cell : mylib90/INVD2
```

max_rise	current	estimate
input net delay	0.102954	0.052354
stage delay	0.000240	0.000120
cell delay	0.371027	0.175534
output net delay	0.206952	0.110121
buffer delay	0.023532	0.013895
delta delay	0.140543	0.051518
arrival time	0.371027	0.175534
slack	0.304100	0.499593
transition		
cell input	0.202001	0.101001
cell output	0.252001	0.151001
load input	0.261001	0.161001

Here the design rule checking estimations include all pins of the buffer being inserted, all pins of the driver cell and slack-critical load pin.

Fig 4.17 estimate_eco -type insert_buffer

CHAPTER 5

IMPROVEMENTS TO TIMING ECO FLOW

5.1 PHYSICALLY AWARE ECO

With available placement information, placement congestion and blockages can be considered during ECO flow and precise ECO guidance can be provided with location information. ECO guidance with location and accurate timing estimation ensures predictable signoff timing closure. ECO can also utilize available space along the net route to increase success rates for ECO fixing in congested regions. Expanding the search space from the proximity of the driver or load pin to the entire net route vastly increases the possibility of an available space for buffer insertion. Main use of physically aware ECO is it prevents cell displacement by constraining cell upsizing to the available neighboring free space and recognizes placement blockage and inserts an ECO buffer on route.

Along with Verilog Netlist, SDC Files, and Libraries, parasitic information (SPEF), physically aware ECO takes extra inputs which are tabulated in below figure.

Type of Data required	Information	Found inside	Can be written from
Library Technology Information	Site info, Routing layer characteristic, VIA details, etc..	LEF	MilkyWay Libraries
Library Cell Physical Information	Cell Layout details – cell dimensions, pin geometries, site classification	LEF	MilkyWay Libraries
Design's Physical Layout	Cell Placement, Routing, row definitions, placement and routing blockages, etc.	DEF	MilkyWay Design Database

Fig 5.1 Inputs for physically aware ECO

DEF file:

- Physical aspects of a design: Die size, Connectivity, Physical location of cells and macros on the chip
- Floor-planning information: Standard cell rows, Placement and routing blockage, Placement constraints, Power domain boundaries

- Routing information: Metal layer used, Routing congestion

Fig 5.2 DEF file

Routing aware to improve fix rates

- On route buffering to fix long nets
- Load splitting to fix high fanout nets
- Regroup nets to fix with fewer buffers

Placement and blockage aware to avoid large displacements

- Use multiple free space for best results
- Account for placement blockage

Fig 5.3 Examples of route aware ECO [24]

Fig 5.4 Example of placement aware ECO [24]

Fig 5.5 Example of congestion aware ECO [24]

To perform physically-aware ECO fixing:

1. Enable the reading of parasitic with location data by setting the `read_parasitics_load_locations` variable.
2. Specify ECO options and read the physical data by using the `set_eco_options` command.

```
pt_shell> set_eco_options \
    -physical_lib_path lef_files \
    -physical_design_path def_files \
    -physical_constraint_file physical_constraint_file \
    -physical_lib_constraint_file spacing_rule_file_list \
    -filler_cell_names cell_names \
    -log_file my_log \
```

3. Preserve specific cells, nets, designs, and library cells by using the `set_dont_touch` command, which applies the `dont_touch` attribute to the specified objects.

4. Check LEF/DEF files for missing, incomplete, or problematic data by running the `check_eco` command.

5. Run ECO fixing with these commands

```
fix_eco_timing -physical_mode open_site | occupied_site
```

- `occupied_site` – Places or resizes cells even if no open sites are available, appropriate for an early-stage ECO or a high utilization design; results in higher fix rates due to a more aggressive approach.
- `open_site` – Places cells only in open sites, appropriate for a late-stage ECO or a low utilization design; results in smaller cell displacement due to a more conservative approach

```
size_cell {syn_inc_1} {and06x5}
size_cell {core/wishbone/rx_fifo/U196} {buf12x5}
size_cell {post_cts_opt_12} {inv06x5}
insert_buffer [get_pins {eth_top_B5R_top_inst/eth_top_m_wb_dat_o_21_bsr81/U1/Z}] buf12x5 -new_net_names {eco_net1} -new_cell_names {eco_buf1}
insert_buffer [get_pins {core/wishbone/rx_fifo/c3292/U136/Z}] buf12x5 -new_net_names {eco_net2} -new_cell_names {eco_buf2}
```

```
add_buffer_on_route [get_net -of {post_cts_opt_25/o}] -user_specified_buffers
{ eco_cap_buf1 bufd12x5 167.643 139.536 0 eco_tran_buf1 buf06x5 121.986 140.128 0} -no_legalize

set_cell_location -coordinates {167.5080 139.2640} -orientation s [get_cells eco_cap_buf1 -hier]
set_cell_location -coordinates {121.8780 139.8080} -orientation s [get_cells eco_tran_buf1 -hier]
insert_buffer [get_pins {syn_10/b}] buf03x5 -new_net_names {eco_net1} -new_cell_names {eco_buf1} -location {171.3420 100.3680} -orientation N
```

Fig 5.6 Difference between Logical aware ECO patch and physically aware ECO patch

During ECO flow we can also specify the margin for setup/ hold fix. For example, if majority of the paths are violating hold by margin of 0 to -500ps, we can fix negative hold paths in the range 0 to -500ps, while ignoring those with negative margin worse than -500.

Fig 5.7 Margin based setup/ hold fix

5.2 ECO BY INCREMENTAL SPEF EXTRACTION

Sometimes, the new netlist to be produced may be an incremental change over an existing one. In such a case, there may not be the need to go over the same cycle of complete synthesis, placement and routing. One such technique is ECO extraction using StarRC. The StarRC tool provides several options to reduce turnaround time by performing extraction only on the ECO-affected nets. StarRC generates an incremental parasitic file with changes due to buffer insertions, cell insertions, cell legalization, or net rerouting. This results in a reduced standard parasitic exchange format (SPEF). This flow improves productivity in large designs by retaining the netlist edits already performed in primetime. We rerun timing analysis with the retained netlist edits and the incremental parasitic data.

Fig 5.8 a. Usual ECO flow with full chip parasitic extraction. b. ECO with incremental SPEF extraction

- Full-design parasitic extraction – StarRC generates a new full-design parasitic file that matches the new netlist. Rerun timing analysis with the new netlist and parasitic files.
- Incremental parasitic extraction – StarRC generates an incremental parasitic file with changes due to buffer insertions, cell insertions, cell legalization, or net rerouting. This results in a reduced Standard Parasitic Exchange Format (SPEF) file. This flow improves productivity in large designs by retaining the netlist edits already performed in timing run.

To run the ECO flow with incremental parasitic extraction, follow these steps

1. In PrimeTime, run timing analysis

```
read_verilog ...
read_sdc ...
read_parasitics my_spef.spef -keep_capacitive_coupling
update_timing
```

2. Fix timing violations, generate a change list file for IC Compiler and save the session
3. In the IC Compiler place-and-route tool, read the change list and implement the changes.
4. In the StarRC parasitic extraction tool, read the updated design and run incremental parasitic extraction.
5. In PrimeTime, restore the previous session and read the incremental parasitics

```
restore_session my_session
read_parasitics -keep_capacitive_coupling original.SPEF \
-eco incremental.SPEF
```

5.3 ECO IN DMSA ENVIRONMENT

It is not sufficient to perform the timing analysis only in functional mode and nominal PVT corner. In order to ensure the correct operation of the chip, timing analysis must be performed under various operating conditions (including operating voltages and extreme temperatures) & various operating modes (including functional, scan). A scenario is a combination of operating conditions and operating modes. The number of scenarios is given by,

Scenarios = [Sets of operating conditions] X [Modes]

Mode	Corner
Functional	Best
JTAG	Typical/ Nominal
ATPG_shift	Worst
ATPG_Capture	

Table 5.1 Multi Corner Multi Mode

With the help of Distributed Multi Scenario Analysis (DMSA) it is possible to analyze several scenario in parallel. DMSA master process sets up difference scenario timing run in different hosts running in parallel, instead of running each scenario sequentially. Thus the overall turnaround time required to run and analyze multiple scenario is greatly reduced by using DMSA. Also each scenario share some common set of data which helps in reducing total runtime, resource and manual effort. So performing ECO in DMSA environment helps us in understanding the effect of ECO patch in different scenarios simultaneously with less resource, runtime and effort.

Here the processing of different scenarios is distributed across different hosts using the command `remote_execute`. Using DMSA we can check the effect of ECO in all possible scenario (all corner & all mode) or only in some important/ dominant scenario as shown in the figure.

Dominant ECO scenarios	All ECO scenarios
<pre>create_scenario {D1 D2 D3} remote_execute { update_timing } #reports remote_execute {set_eco_option check_eco} fix_eco_xx -physical_mode #reports remote_execute {write_changes -format eco \ -output change_list.eco write_changes -format icctl \ -output change_list.icctl}</pre>	<pre>create_scenario {D1 D2 D3 O1 O2 .. On} remote_execute { update_timing } #reports remote_execute {set_eco_option check_eco} remote_execute {read_eco_changes \ change_list.eco} # Reports # Additional ECO steps (optional) # Write changes for IC Compiler # Implement ECO in IC Compiler # Check results in PrimeTime</pre>

Fig 5.9 Performing ECO in DMSA environment

Fig 5.10 DMSA Flow

Mode merging technology retains the benefit of writing individual modes, while providing an automated path to generate superset modes to minimize ECO and timing closure turnaround time. This avoids the risk and complexity of manual mode merging, while keeping the runtime and resource reduction benefits of merged modes. For example, in figure, line joining two modes (for example, m2 and m7) indicates that they can be merged. A ‘superset’ is a group of modes that can all be merged with one another. Notice how modes m3 and m8 can be merged, but mode m8 cannot be merged with any other modes, so m3 and m8 are merged as part of a separate group, M2.

Fig 5.11 Mode compatibility graph

Fig 5.12 Two modes that can be automatically merged

In this example, the merged mode does not retain the set_case_analysis settings in the individual modes. The merged mode constraints add a set_disable_timing constraint on the SEL input port, since it is not active in any of the original modes.

Fig 5.13 Two modes that cannot be automatically merged

In this example, mode3 and mode4 cannot be merged since the gclk_model1 generated clock in mode3 would block the propagation of the clk_mode2 clock in mode4.

The following script is a typical multi-scenario master script.

```
# Requires scenario swapping just one time
remote_execute {
  set_dont_touch $dont_touch_list
  set_dont_use $dont_use_list
  set_eco_alternative_area_ratio_threshold 2
  update_timing
}

fix_eco_timing -type setup

# Requires scenario swapping just one time
remote_execute {
  report_analysis_coverage
  report_timing -delay_type max ...
  report_timing -delay_type min ...
  report_constraint -all_violators ...
}

# Minimum reports at master to minimize scenario swapping
report_constraint -all_violators ...

# Write changes to only one scenario to avoid scenario swapping
current_scenario scen1
remote_execute { write_changes -output my_eco.tcl }
```

5.4 FULL CHIP MIN DELAY CONVERGENCE

Hyperscale context flow is primetime official capability which let the partition level runs to have all relevant full chip point of view. From full chip timing run, context data is generated for all the comers. This context data is in binary format containing all the details regarding clock source latency, CRPR (Clock Reconvergence Pessimism Removal), AOCVM/POCVM, clock and data Trans/ Cap values, Input & Output delay, Exceptions propagation etc.

Hyperscale context flow greatly help in shortening the overall interface min (hold) delay fix time by letting the partition level runs to close all the interface hold issues by using the full chip constraints. So the internal paths which are affected by full chip are efficiently fixed and only real timing issues are focused rather than by dictated eco list. Also it helps in partition signoff quality cleanup.

Steps to follow:

- Generating full chip timing model with context data.
- Generating the port list per partition where hold fix is needed.

- The context data thus generated will be taken by implementation team to generate partition level timing runs with context data and relevant full chip information.
- Propagate context data and update timing. report_context <port_name> will give the context input on specific port.
- Now timing ECO can be run with the context session + port list. Interface post fix margin are analyzed to find the unfixable paths.
- Using partition level DBs, a new full chip model is generated and the feedback is taken regarding unfixable paths in next iteration.

Fig 5.14 Min delay convergence flow using context

CHAPTER 6

SIMULTANEOUS DATA PATH AND CLOCK PATH ENGINEERING CHANGE ORDER

Clock path rescheduling means performing clock push/ pull (Clock tuning) by inserting or removing clock buffers. Currently primetime ECO supports all the options of buffer insertion and gate sizing. But what primetime ECO doesn't support is clock ECO. In Clock ECO the main idea is to utilize the useful skew, to fix the violating paths.

6.1 USEFUL SKEW CONCEPTS

Usually data path optimization is used for fixing most of the timing violations in the design. But with useful skew one can fix violating path by adjusting clock arrival times to the registers or latches.

Fig 6.1 Fixing Timing Violations by Using Clock Skew

But useful skew approach cannot improve timing for looping paths from a register to itself and feedthrough paths from input to output port as shown.

Fig 6.2 Limitations of useful skew approach

6.2 PROPOSED METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS CLOCK AND DATA PATH ECO

6.2.1 Major challenges with the proposed method:

1. Finding a common point on the clock tree where the ECO patch can be placed such that it will help in fixing multiple failing end points.
2. Checking the fanout cone of the clock tree restructuring / resizing element, so that restructuring doesn't result in negative slack across the paths which were not failing before. i.e Fixing negative margin for some path shouldn't create new paths with negative slack.
3. Fix should be MCMC aware (Multi Corner Multi Mode). Before inserting/removing any buffers, we should check its impact on setup/ hold across multiple corner including max, min, typical and across multiple modes including scan, functional.
4. If clock rescheduling is not possible or not feasible, then performing regular data path optimization by buffer insertion or gate sizing.

Fig 6.3 Flow chart of the proposed algorithm

6.2.2 Prerequisites before performing clock ECO:

- Check clock tree for missing or incorrect constraints or definitions using `check_clock_tree`
- Use a quick run of clock tree synthesis to determine and apply clock latencies

- Ensure that the clock latency specifications on clock pins in the clock structure are correct
- Remove any ideal latencies set on the clock network (remove_ideal_latency)
- Ensure that high fanout nets are marked as ideal or run high-fanout net synthesis on these net
- Optimize the design to minimize timing violations

6.2.3 Approach & algorithm for clock path ECO:

The algorithm here tries to find out a point (cell) in the clock tree, which is common to multiple failing end points in the design. Inserting an ECO patch, by clock rescheduling at this common point helps in fixing the timing violation across multiple failing end points, instead of performing data path ECO on all paths.

The figure 6.4 shows the main advantage of clock path ECO. Suppose there are multiple paths which are violating setup as shown in row 2. Performing data path ECO will try to upsize the cells on all the failing paths as shown in Fig 6.4b, which will unnecessarily results in area and power overhead. In such case, finding a common point in clock tree which is driving all these failing end points and inserting few buffers on clock path will fix the setup violation across all these failing paths as shown in Fig 6.4c. If there is no such common point in clock tree, then the algorithm performs usual data path fixing by gate sizing or insert buffer.

6.4 (a)

6.4 (b)

6.4 (c)

Fig 6.4 (a) All FlipFlop in row2 are violating setup (b) Data path ECO by gate upsizing (c) Clock path ECO by clock push

Before performing clock ECO, CTS done and is stable with balanced skew and Clock transition violations should be fixed prior to clock rescheduling. Because clock transition creates unnecessary skew and results in inaccurate delay calculations.

Approach & algorithm for clock path ECO

Algorithm 1: Clock path ECO

```
1: procedure Clockpath_ECO (FEP_list, corner, mode)
2: Foreach endpoint in FEP_list
3:   get_timing_path –through CLK pin of FEP
4:   Foreach i in $path
5:     list_i<- get_points in the clk path
6:   end
7: end
8: sort all list. Backtrace each list to find common point
9: if (common_point)
10:  check slack for clock push/ pull in multiple corner and mode
11:  if (safe_slack_margin)
12:    insert / remove buffers
13:  else
14:  proc (Datapath_ECO)
15:end procedure
```

The clock ECO algorithm takes a set of Failing End Points as input. The clock pins of each FEP are backtraced and all points in clock path are stored in separate lists. Each list is sorted and first common clock buffer amongst all lists is greped. Then the slack checking is done across multiple corners and multiple modes before pushing / pulling clock. A design will have,

- Multiple paths to each end point
- Multiple paths from each start point
- Inter clock relationships

Fig 6.5 Flop in a design connected to multiple start and end points

The slack checking is done to ensure the positive safe margin at the fanout cone of clock tree restructuring element and exploit this safe margin (useful skew) to fix negative slack on violating path. If anyone path at the fanout cone has negative margin, then it is

not preferred to do clock push/ pull. Regular data path ECO is preferred in such case. Figure 6.6 and 6.7 shows how the slack checking is done before clock push / pull.

Fig 6.6 slack checking before clock push (inserting clock buffer)

Fig 6.7 slack checking before clock pull (removing clock buffer)

6.2.4 Approach & algorithm for data path ECO:

The approach for data path ECO is same as discussed in chapter 4. For making the ECO physically aware, DEF file (Design Exchange Format) is taken as input. Even with the routed design, we can perform ECO by adding buffers on route. Thus exact location where the buffer needs to be added is specified in the ECO script. After sourcing the ECO script legalization of placement must be done. To verify the correct operation of design under different operating conditions (extreme temperature & operating voltages) and different operating modes (functional & scan), we require several parallel timing runs. But by using DMSA instead of analyzing each scenarios in sequence, we can analyze several scenarios in parallel. Different scenarios are remotely executed in different hosts running in parallel thus reducing the overall turnaround time / run time, resources and

effort. Also the effect of on chip variation can be analyzed in DMSA environment by providing timing derate values.

Approach & algorithm for data path ECO

Algorithm 2: Data path ECO

```
1: procedure Datapath_ECO (path_group,  
2: No.of iterations, corner, mode)  
3: Foreach path in design  
4:   if (slack < 0) then  
5:     get_timing_path through FEP  
6:     Foreach point in violating path  
7:       get delay increment  
8:       if (delay increment > tran limit)  
9:         Input tran is bad. Do DRC fix  
10:      else  
11:        current_drive <- get_drive_strength (cell)  
12:        Foreach cell in library  
13:          if (get_drive_strength($cell) > current_drive)  
14:            perform size_cell  
15:          else perform Vt swap  
16:        end  
17:      end  
18:    end  
19: update_timing in all corners and modes  
20: perform next iteration  
21: end procedure
```

Final algorithm is a wrapper written on top of clock path ECO and data path ECO algorithms. It first calls the clock path ECO procedure. If all paths are not fixed by clock rescheduling, then data path ECO procedure is called.

Algorithm 3: Clock path + Data path ECO

```
1: procedure Simultaneous_ECO (path_group, FEP_list,  
Corner, mode)  
2: Execute Clockpath_ECO (FEP_list, corner, mode)  
for all clock, corners and modes  
3: set n report_timing -slack_lesser_than 0  
4: size_of_collection n not_equal_to 0  
5: Execute Datapath_ECO (path_group, No.of iterations,  
Corner, mode) for all path_group, corners and modes  
6: end procedure
```

CHAPTER 7

RESULTS, CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

7.1 TIMING ECO RESULTS

The presented algorithm is implemented as a tcl script (Tool Command Language) in a UNIX machine with i5 core, 4GB RAM, 2.5 GHz CPU. Several industrial designs are taken for experimental purpose. Synopsys Primitime tool version k-2015 is used as a main tool for performing timing analysis. Table 7.1 shows the comparison of Worst Negative Slack WNS, Total Negative Slack TNS, Failing End Points FEP and number of size cell commands between data path ECO using proposed algorithm and ECO using existing Primitime ECO utility (fix_eco_timing).

	Before ECO			After Primitime_ECO				DataPath ECO using proposed Algorithm			
	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP	size cell commands	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP	size cell commands
Design A	170	17087	457	170	2660	32	7202	144	3848	102	14880
Design B	354	22839	93	354	22541	86	36	354	22802	93	84
Design C	2111	75945	183	2111	73681	170	143	2108	75477	180	583
Design D	17329	254267	2766	1780	17889	190	10332	1810	21189	240	16883
Design E	235	5716	58	235	574	4	346	235	589	10	559
Design F	610	46623	1970	500	2123	23	708	502	19553	90	2421
Design G	282	24100	849	289	22615	749	3175	282	18006	608	4008
Design H	114	1129	57	14	48	2	2733	124	764	15	2943
Design I	15708	985856	1185	2225	112015	586	4534	10533	334731	980	7333
Design J	4058	45449	208	4058	35807	171	935	4058	35078	180	724

Table 7.1 WNS, TNS and FEP comparison between PT_ECO and DataPath ECO using proposed algorithm

Fix rate %	After Primitime_ECO			DataPath ECO using proposed Algorithm		
	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP
Design A	0	84.43261	92.99781	15.29412	77.47996	77.68053
Design B	0	1.304786	7.526882	0	0.162004	0
Design C	0	2.981105	7.103825	0.142113	0.616235	1.639344
Design D	89.7282	92.96448	93.13087	89.55508	91.66663	91.32321
Design E	0	89.95801	93.10345	0	89.69559	82.75862
Design F	18.03279	95.44645	98.83249	17.70492	58.06147	95.43147
Design G	-2.48227	6.161826	11.77856	0	25.28631	28.38634
Design H	87.7193	95.74845	96.49123	-8.77193	32.3295	73.68421
Design I	85.83524	88.63779	50.54852	32.945	66.04666	17.29958
Design J	0	21.21499	17.78846	0	22.81898	13.46154

Table 7.2 Fix rate comparison between PT_ECO and DataPath ECO using proposed algorithm

Table 7.2 shows the corresponding fix rate WRT Worst Negative Slack WNS, Total Negative Slack TNS, and Failing End Points FEP in data path ECO and primetime ECO. The Figure 7.1 shows the respective fix rate interms of WNS, TNS, and FEP. The proposed algorithm results comparably matches with the existing primetime utility, also the runtime using proposed algorithm is much less compared to PT_ECO flow.

Fig 7.1 a. Fix rate using PT_ECO

Fig 7.1 b. Fix rate using proposed algorithm for DataPath ECO

Figure 7.2 and 7.3 shows the ECO summary for setup and hold fix. The ECO summary contains the details like total number of buffers inserted or total number of gate resized, increase in area after ECO, number of violating endpoints which are fixed after ECO, and the values of WNS, TNS and FEP after ECO.

```

Final ECO Summary:
-----
Number of insert_buffer commands          107
Total number of commands                  107
Area increased by buffer insertion        116.00
Total area increased                      116.00

Fixing Summary:
-----
Total violating endpoints found           6776
Total violating endpoints fixed           6776
Total violating endpoints remaining        0
Total percentage of violations fixed      100.0%

Setup violations
-----
                Total  reg->reg  in->reg  reg->out  in->out
-----
WNS  -2158.93      0.00      0.00  -2158.93  0.00
TNS  -79002.48     0.00      0.00 -79002.48  0.00
NUM      78         0         0         78       0
-----

```

Fig 7.2 Example of primetime ECO summary after Setup fix

```

Final ECO Summary:
-----
Number of size_cell commands              63
Number of insert_buffer commands         2001
Total number of commands                 2064
Area increased by cell sizing             -0.72
Area increased by buffer insertion        284.02
Total area increased                     283.30

Fixing Summary:
-----
Total violating endpoints found           2523
Total violating endpoints fixed           2456
Total violating endpoints remaining        67
Total percentage of violations fixed      97.3%

Hold violations
-----
                Total  reg->reg  in->reg  reg->out  in->out
-----
WNS  -2370.07     -2370.07  0.00    0.00    0.00
TNS  -37060.88   -37060.88  0.00    0.00    0.00
NUM    67         67         0         0         0
-----

```

Fig 7.3 Example of primetime ECOsummary after Hold fix using Resize & Insert buffer

7.2 PHYSICAL AWARE ECO RESULT

Physically aware ECO gives a better fix rate as compared to regular ECO, as it considers the placement congestion, blockages and routing congestion during buffer insertion or gate resize. The WNS, TNS and FEP improvements by using physically aware ECO is shown in figure 7.4

	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP
Before	125	3295	299
After	125	560	43

Fig 7.4 Result of physically aware ECO

7.3 RESULT OF ECO IN DMSA ENVIRONMENT

Performing ECO using Distributed Multi Scenario Analysis helps in reducing the manual effort of analyzing the timing violations across multiple scenarios. Since some of the common files like netlist, SPEF, libraries are shared across multiple corners and modes; the resource usage is greatly reduced. The improvement in setup and hold WNS, TNS and FEP using ECO in DMSA is illustrated in the below figures.

SETUP	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP
Before	2158	79002	78
After	957	29449	32

Fig 7.5 Setup improvement after ECO in DMSA environment

HOLD	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP
Before	520	19404	1386
After	0	0	0

Fig 7.6 Hold improvement after ECO in DMSA environment

7.4 POWER ECO RESULT

Primetime PTPX also provides facilities to perform power ECO. The following figures give the comparison of power before ECO and after ECO

Power before ECO:

Power Group	Internal Power	Switching Power	Leakage Power	Total Power	(%)
clock_network	2.507e-03	1.696e-03	1.027e-04	4.307e-03	(60.06%)
register	3.995e-04	5.527e-05	3.022e-04	7.570e-04	(10.56%)
combinational	5.894e-04	7.033e-04	4.899e-04	1.783e-03	(24.86%)
sequential	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	(0.00%)
memory	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	(0.00%)
io_pad	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	(0.00%)
black_box	2.597e-04	1.674e-05	4.822e-05	3.246e-04	(4.53%)
Net Switching Power	= 2.472e-03	(34.47%)			
Cell Internal Power	= 3.756e-03	(52.38%)			
Cell Leakage Power	= 9.430e-04	(13.15%)			
Total Power	= 7.171e-03	(100.00%)			

Power after ECO:

Final ECO Summary:					
Number of size_cell commands				66818	
Initial total cell area				24205.82	
Final total cell area				23128.47	
Total cell area decreased				1077.35	
Percentage of total cell area decreased				4.5%	
Percentage of datapath cell area decreased				4.7%	
Power Group	Internal Power	Switching Power	Leakage Power	Total Power	(%)
clock_network	2.484e-03	1.680e-03	1.027e-04	4.267e-03	(61.88%)
register	3.936e-04	5.484e-05	2.916e-04	7.401e-04	(10.73%)
combinational	5.371e-04	6.827e-04	3.473e-04	1.567e-03	(22.73%)
sequential	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	(0.00%)
memory	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	(0.00%)
io_pad	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	(0.00%)
black_box	2.594e-04	1.433e-05	4.777e-05	3.215e-04	(4.66%)
Net Switching Power	= 2.432e-03	(35.27%)			
Cell Internal Power	= 3.674e-03	(53.29%)			
Cell Leakage Power	= 7.893e-04	(11.45%)			
Total Power	= 6.895e-03	(100.00%)			

Fig 7.7 ECO summary before and after power ECO

7.5 DRC ECO RESULT

Figure 7.8 shows the improvement in max capacitance violation by using cell sizing. In similar way other DRC violations like max transition, max fanout can be addressed.

DRC before ECO:

Design Rules	
Total Number of Nets:	225250
Nets with Violations:	5628
Max Trans Violations:	212
Max Cap Violations:	3311
Max Fanout Violations:	2565

Design Rule Violations	
Total No. of Pins in Design:	513825
clock_gating_setup Count:	2
max_capacitance Count:	50
clock_gating_setup Cost:	-13.35
max_capacitance Cost:	-30.81
Total DRC Cost:	-44.16

DRC after ECO:

Final ECO Summary:	
Number of size_cell commands	42
Total number of commands	42
Area increased by cell sizing	0.13
Total area increased	0.13

Design Rule Violations	
Total No. of Pins in Design:	513825
clock_gating_setup Count:	2
max_capacitance Count:	13
clock_gating_setup Cost:	-13.35
max_capacitance Cost:	-25.67
Total DRC Cost:	-39.03

Fig 7.8 ECO summary before and after DRC ECO

7.6 RESULT OF ECO DURING MIN DELAY CONVERGENCE USING CONTEXT FLOW

The improvement in setup and hold violations by hyper scale context flow is tabulated below. We can observe that it greatly contributes in fixing the hold violations

in the design. The experiments showed an improvement of 17.93% in WNS, 57.98% in TNS and 15.77% in FEP.

SETUP	WNS	TNS	FEP
Before	12060	25187293	32903
After	12015	12120152	22250

HOLD	WNS	TNS	FEP
Before	1818	204320	3310
After	1492	85838	2788

7.7 RESULT OF SIMULTANEOUS CLOCK PATH & DATA PATH ECO

Two sets of experiments are done on the same designs. One by performing ECO only using data path fixing. Other by performing clock ECO followed by data path ECO. The corresponding results are shown in table 7.3 and the fix rate is shown in Table 7.4 AND Figure 7.9. The Figure 7.10 shows the size of ECO patch before and after using clock rescheduling. It is clearly observed that using clock path ECO significantly reduce the size of ECO patch i.e less number of resize and insert buffer commands. Thus the overall amount of area increased after ECO is 56.6 % less in clock + data ECO as compared to data ECO alone. This highlights the advantage of clock path rescheduling.

	DataPath ECO using proposed Algorithm				ClockPath + DataPath ECO using proposed algorithm			
	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP	ECO patch size	WNS (-)	TNS (-)	FEP	ECO patch size
				(size cell)				(insert buffer + size cell)
Design A	144	3848	102	14880	120	1856	23	2760
Design B	354	22802	93	84	354	16381	66	22
Design C	2108	75477	180	583	908	54775	128	66
Design D	1810	21189	240	16883	1432	15773	165	9860
Design E	235	589	10	559	235	502	5	289
Design F	502	19553	90	2421	525	8090	64	634
Design G	282	18006	608	4008	198	18998	690	2365
Design H	124	764	15	2943	78	459	9	678
Design I	10533	334731	980	7333	4967	110124	691	4056
Design J	4058	35078	180	724	4058	26804	153	703

Table 7.3 WNS, TNS and FEP comparison between only DataPath ECO & Clock + Data Path ECO using proposed algorithm

	WNS (%)	TNS (%)	FEP (%)
Design A	29.41176	89.13794	94.96718
Design B	0	28.27619	29.03226
Design C	56.98721	27.87544	30.05464
Design D	91.7364	93.79668	94.03471
Design E	0	91.21763	91.37931
Design F	13.93443	82.64805	96.75127
Design G	29.78723	21.17012	18.72792
Design H	31.57895	59.34455	84.21053
Design I	68.37917	88.82961	41.68776
Design J	0	41.024	26.44231

Table 7.4 Fix rate using Clock + Data Path ECO using proposed algorithm

Fig 7.9 Fix rate using proposed algorithm for Clock + DataPath ECO

	Data path ECO	Data + Clock path ECO	Area improvement (%)
Design A	14880	2760	81.451613
Design B	84	22	73.809524
Design C	583	66	88.679245
Design D	16883	9860	41.598057
Design E	559	289	48.300537
Design F	2421	634	73.812474
Design G	4008	2365	40.993014
Design H	2943	678	76.962283
Design I	7333	4056	44.688395
Design J	724	703	2.9005525

Table 7.4 ECO patch size comparison between data Eco and Clock + Data Path ECO

Fig 7.10 ECO patch size comparison graph

To conclude, the proposed algorithm shows a better fix rate of 31.7% interms of Worst Negative Slack, 61.9% interms of Total Negative Slack, 60.3% interms of Failing End Points. However the main disadvantage of clock path ECO is that, it creates skew in clock tree and results in imbalanced CTS. So prefer clock tree ECO only if it targets fixing a bunch of failing end points. Performing clock rescheduling to fix one / two paths is not advisable.

7.7 FUTURE WORK

Currently the proposed algorithm takes a set of Failing End Points and tries to find a point where ECO patch can be inserted in clock path. The algorithm can be extended to work for a bigger design, where the input will the entire design details instead of a set of failing end points. Also the algorithm can be made to work as a standalone tool by coding it in C/ C++ programming language instead of tool command language.

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